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**The Environmental Year of the Republic of Congo.
*The Progressive Development of Environmental
Law in 2019.***

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Abstract

The Republic of Congo has fostered significant development of environmental law and policy over the years. However, in recent years, since 2015 with the adoption of the Paris Agreement on Climate Change, the Republic of Congo has been characterized by significant legislative activity, which is also supported by environmental diplomacy internationally. In this article, Dr. Aubin Nzaou presents the developments during the year 2019. These are of a dual nature. On the one hand, international environmental law marked by the adoption of many instruments of international law, at the universal level, such as the Minamata Convention on Mercury, or at the level of the African Union, including the ratification of the Agreement Establishing the African Continental Free Trade Area. On the other hand, developments in national legislation highlight the adoption of numerous laws and regulations on various elements of the environment, energy and natural resources, such as Marine Environment, Meteorological and Hydrological Data, The Resource Management, The Climate Change, The Biodiversity, The Environmental Actors, etc. It is therefore these aspects that this article undertakes to analyze.

Keywords

Environment in Congo, ratification of Agreement Establishing the African Continental Free Trade Area, marine environment and climate change in Congo, Congolese environmental law, energy, natural resources.

In 2019, the Republic of Congo has incorporated many instruments of international environmental law into its legal order, introduced new legislation, and conducted significant negotiations with several international partners, both public and private.

(1) International Environmental Law

(A) Agreement Establishing the African Continental Free Trade Area

On 7 February, the parliament authorized the government (Authorization Act 2-2019) to ratify the Agreement Establishing the African Continental Free Trade Area. Pursuant to the aspirations set out in Agenda 2063 to create a continental market favorable to the free movement of people, capital, goods, and services, the Agreement Establishing the African Continental Free Trade Area, reached on 21 March 2018, in Kigali, Rwanda, by member states of the African Union, set out the framework for strengthening continental economic integration. In accordance with the terms of its Article 3, it is an economic legal instrument—in essence—but which includes a Protocol on Trade in Services recognizing the right of States Parties to lay down provisions of services on their territory and to foster relevant regulations, in support of the legitimate objectives of sustainable development and environmental protection, as follows:

‘RECOGNISING the right of State Parties to regulate in pursuit of national policy objectives, and to introduce new regulations (...), including competitiveness, consumer protection and overall sustainable development with respect to the degree of the development of services regulations in

different countries, the particular need for State Parties to exercise this right, without compromising consumer protection, environmental protection, and overall sustainable development.' (Para. 5)

By the Decree of 7 February (Decree No. 2019-32), this international agreement was definitively ratified. Having regard to the necessity of new measures related to free trade between African countries, the government appeared to conceptualize bilateral trade initiatives.

(B) Minamata Convention on Mercury

On 17 May, the government secured the authorization to ratify the Minamata Convention on Mercury. In this regard, the parliament, by means of an Authorization Act No. 11-2019, accepted the ratification process to be performed. The Presidential Decree (No. 2019-129) was issued on the same date in order to consolidate the municipal law apparatus of human health protection and environmental conservation against 'anthropogenic emissions and releases of mercury and mercury compounds.' (Article 1).

In accordance with article 1 of the Decree, the government, accepting this instrument into the internal legal system, adhere to the global consensus that emphasizes the dangerousness of mercury as a chemical, including long-range atmospheric spread, persistence in the environment once introduced by anthropogenic activity, the potential for 'bio-accumulation in ecosystems and [the] significant adverse effects on human health and the environment.'

From the outset, it is incumbent upon the government to use any lawful means to identify, ‘individual stocks of mercury or mercury compounds of more than 50 metric tons and sources of mercury supply producing stocks of more than 10 metric tons per year in its territory.’ Given the important development of mining activities in many regions, the government, supported by civil society actors should carry out technical and administrative monitoring.

Then, it should take a firm step to ensure that, wherever ‘the existence of excess mercury from the decommissioning of chlorine-alkali plants’ is found out, appropriate measures to dispose of it, ‘in accordance with ecologically sound management guidelines paragraph 3(a) of Article 11’, by resorting to means which preclude recovery, recycling, regeneration, direct reuse or any other use. (Article 3, Para. 5).

By virtue of the provisions of Article 3 of the Minamata Convention on Mercury, in particular of subsections 6 and 7, the Republic of Congo—subject to the provisions—shall not allow the export of mercury or import from a non-Party. On behalf of those provisions:

‘Each Party shall not allow the import of mercury from a non-Party to whom it will provide its written consent unless the non-Party has provided certification (...) (b).’

(C) International Solar Alliance (ISA)

Having regard to its pledge of enhancing, for a significant part, the role of renewable energies in

its energy mix, the Republic of Congo also adheres to another international instrument, the Framework Agreement on the Establishment of the International Solar Alliance (ISA), on 17 May. As stated above, this new pathway is aimed at supporting the implementation of solar energy policy and the development of equipment and appropriate technologies related to solar energy at the country-wide level. The Alliance's purpose is to help states to identify and then to address collectively, 'Key common challenges to the scaling up of solar energy in the line with [every state] needs.' (Article 1).

It should be noted that the government is engaged to participate in coordinated measures and to perform actions likely to support, on a voluntary basis, the harmonising and aggregating demand for the funding necessary for solar energy development projects, 'solar technologies, innovation, research and development and capacity building.' ISA members are bound to cooperate and maintain mutually beneficial relationships with all relevant actors, including international organizations, multi-stakeholders, and non-Member States.

This status of State Member proceeds on the assumption that for the implementation of the actions, the government shall designate a national focal point. The latter will be part of the ISA's permanent network of correspondents in the countries of the World.

The national focal points role is to collaborate:

' (...) with each other and with relevant stakeholders in order to identify areas of common interest, and to formulate proposals for programs

and recommendations to the Secretariat with regard to the implementation of the ISA's objectives.'

Therefore, it is quite clear that ASI's programs and support to public policies on energy transition are valuable assets and benefit this initiative will confer.

(2) National Legislation

(A) Marin Environment

In February, after a long round of discussion, the parliament finally adopted an Act enforcing the national legislation on marine areas (Act 5-2019). By means of legal provisions, it states clearly that naval vessel commanders and state aircraft captains are competent *prima facie* in terms of use of coercion and force at sea and in continental waters. In this regard, it should be observed those authorities are entitled to use force and to exercise control and coercive measures on Congolese-flagged ships and boats, in particular, all maritime and continental waters, mostly outside areas under the jurisdiction of other states under the international law of the sea.

The government continued enhancing the series of legal instruments initiated in this framework in May. Indeed, the presidential Decree (No. 2019-125) was issued to organize and coordinate the state's action at sea and in continental waters. The latter sets out the framework for the organization and coordination of the Congolese state's action at sea and in continental waters. Its Article 2 broadens the ambit of this action, which includes environmental protection and pollution control,

control of illegal fishing, monitoring, and control of the exploitation of fisheries resources, marine, and river scientific research, etc.

(B) Meteorological and Hydrological Data

On 17 January, in light of diverse circumstances related to the need for updated meteorological and hydrological data, a ministerial Order instituted a project entitled "monitoring the dynamics of the coastline at Pointe-Noire" (Order 542-2019). Its purpose is, in general, to obtain and exploit long sets of basic meteorological and hydrological data from the Congolese coastal zone in order to detect climate signals. In support of this purpose, the project is aimed at conducting necessary studies of the water masses; namely their surface and subsurface; their movements and extensions every year; the structure generated by those movements, and the fortifications of nutrient salts and plankton resulting from those movements. It is worth recalling that the project also includes studies on marine wildlife, population dynamics of the main fish species and productivity for the management of Congolese fisheries. Yet, the project is organised under the authority of the Ministry of Scientific Research and Technological Innovation.

From the above, it-therefore-clearly appears that the project, as it has been formulated, is rooted in the tradition of earlier Order 13480 of 12 December 2018 authorizing a marine scientific research campaign. The latter was known as hydro-oceanographic measurements, also designated "ZMATO 2019" in maritime waters under Congolese jurisdiction. Such continuity was fostered by the ministerial Decree of 7 February (Decree No. 2030)

which authorizes a French research institute to carry out campaigns of seabed surveys.

(C) The Resource Management

The government undertook the work of giving natural resources management's momentum in December 2018. The Presidential Decree No. 2018-484 issued on 26 December 2018 contained recitals which settled out the allocations, composition, and operation of the customarily owned land recognition commission. In March 2019, a ministerial Order was issued to prescribe the licence fee applicable to operators in the power sector (Order 5168 of 25 March). The ministerial Order consequently enacted the percentage of licence fee implemented whenever powers operators carry out their sale's activity or any trade relating to the electricity sector. In itself, and regardless of many other circumstances, such a situation was likely to be applied to the water sector.

As a result, another ministerial Order, applicable to the intervention of operators in the water and sanitation sector, was laid down on 25 March. By all means, the ministerial Order aimed at applying licence fees to autonomous water producers. It is then clearly established that any system of autonomous water production should comply with the administrative authorization regime (Order 5169).

Finally, a ministerial Order (Order 6390-2019) of 8 April approved the industrial transformation agreement for the development of the Kimandou and Mabombo forestry units. The latter the instrument was issued in order to develop, in particular from a sustainable perspective, the Kimandou, and Mabombo

forestry units located respectively in the Southern 8 (Sibiti) and Madingou forest units located in the region of Lekoumou, on the one hand, and Bouenza, on the other hand.

(D) The Climate Change

In January, a ministerial Order was issued to combat the harmful effects of climate change. It set out a series of principles applicable to the process of reducing greenhouse gas emissions with regard to deforestation, forest degradation, biodiversity conservation, and increased greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) carbon stocks. It should be noted that the ministerial Order undoubtedly referred to the necessary inclusion of sustainability in forest management. As a result, the broad range of guiding principles for reducing greenhouse gas emissions specify accurately the determining conditions of validation and the process of approbation of REDD projects and programs. Furthermore, the ministerial Order enshrines—in its Article 3—the right to generate and trade carbon credits.

Thus, it is worthwhile to assert that the right extends to individuals and corporations. The credits can be generated from the forests, which belongs to the permanent and the non-permanent forest domain of the State, either under management or by the promoters of emission reduction projects related to deforestation and forest degradation. The authorization will be issued by the Minister for Water and Forests. In addition, in light of these various considerations, the ministerial Order confers a significant meaning to a variety of concepts like sustainable forest management, biodiversity conservation, and forest carbon stocks.

Finally, the Order does exclude the concession of natural forest or a state-owned forest plantation, in the sense that no carbon rights are conferred on their attribute.

(E) The Biodiversity

As response to threats related to the disappearance of ducks in the Republic of Congo, a ministerial Order of 17 January 2019 (543-2019) established a research project whose scope is to study the *in situ* conservation and sustainable use of local duck populations within the national territory. In fact, the project is created within the Ministry of Scientific Research and Technological Innovation, under the authority of the National Institute of Agricultural Research. Its many tasks include the contribution to the preservation of local duck breeds in the Republic of Congo, and growth in the quality of production of local duck breeds. According to the ministerial Order, the project will also identify, at the local level, bred duck varieties, select high-performing strains of locally bred ducks, establish a complete statistical database on the specimen, monitor products, produce quality seed and practice artificial insemination, form, and breed artificial insemination techniques, train, supervise and monitor locally bred and former duck farmers, establish a national database of locally bred duck farmers, redevelop pilot breeding facilities and organize days of exchange of experiences each year.

(F) The Environmental Actors

On 20 February, a ministerial Order (3041-2019) created the Laboratory Physic-Environmental-

Chemistry of the National Research Institute for Exact and Natural Sciences. Its origins should be sought in the provisions of Articles 3 and 4 of Presidential Order (2019-4922) of 9 July 2018, which evoked the necessity of a new actor within the Department of Chemical Sciences of the Scientific Directorate of the National Institute for Research in Exact and Natural Sciences. Yet, to some extent, its ambit will be to support environmental research; conduct physical and chemical analyses of the environment for the benefit of third parties and in particular pollutants; assist and participate in research and promotion of sustainable development; contribute to research and research training in this area.

Then, one year after the adoption of the organic law on the organisation, composition, and operation of the Economic, Social and Environmental Council (No. 27-2018 of 7 August 2018), a Presidential Decree on 28 March 2019 appointed members of the Economic, Social and Environmental Council (Decree 2019-58). In fact, the Economic, Social and Environment Council is an advisory assembly before Congolese public authorities. The scope of its competence extends to the examination of economic, social or environmental developments, from legal or public policies perspective. It should be noted that the council can, on its own initiative, address the economic, social or environmental issues of any kind. Subsequently, the Economic, Social and Environmental Council may also be consulted, by the government, on draft treaties or international agreements, drafts or proposals for legislation, as well as draft decrees falling within its mandate. Yet, except the country budget, any draft economic,

social or environmental development program and plan are referred to the council.

(3) International Environmental Cooperation

On March 11-15, the Republic of Congo associated its voice with the United Nations Environment Assembly and participated in the adoption of UNEA-4 Ministerial Declaration (UNEP/EA.4/L.1).

In June, the Congolese government also participated in the Pre-Summit of Climate Action in Abu Dhabi, the United Arab Emirates, on 29 and 30 June 2019, ahead of the Summit to be held on 23 September 2019 in New York alongside the 74th United Nations General Assembly.

The Republic of Congo actively participated in the 2nd Conference of the Plenipotentiaries of the Abidjan Convention. On 2 July 2019, Congo signed additional protocols to the Abidjan Convention. The latter include: Pointe-Noire Protocol on the Integrated Management of the Coastal Area of West, Central and South Africa; Grand-Bassam Protocol on the regulation of sources of pollution from land or air sources; Malabo on the risks of pollution caused by oil and gas operations and Mangrove protocol.

The government, in partnership with the Central African States Development Bank (BDEAC), convened experts from the sub-region, in September, in Brazzaville, Congo, to adopt a common position which countries should defend during the New York Summit, on 23 September. These experts were able to elaborate and validate a draft declaration, on 6 September, setting out the common position on the proper management and promotion of the potential of Congo's

forests. The meeting was followed by the round table of Ministers of Economic Development and Foreign Affairs of the Member States of the Economic Community of Central African States (CEEAC) on 7 September, in Brazzaville. At the special session, ministers adopted a common position as a prelude to the Climate Action Summit.

On September 12-13, participants met in Brazzaville for the first meeting of the Steering Committee of the study of the Congo Basin Bleu Fund. Participants were able to elaborate and issue several requisite recommendations. Also, with the support of multilateral partners, the second meeting of the Steering Committee of the study of the Congo Basin Bleu Fund was held again—in Brazzaville—on 4-5 November 2019.

It is noteworthy that the government attended the Climate Action Summit in New York, the United States, on 23 September. In this sense, the government defended the common position of Congo Basin countries on the need for a reinforced action on forest management in the context of climate change.

Further, in accordance with its own commitment to combating climate change, the government also acted decisively during the 4th African Ministerial Conference for Disaster Risk Reduction held in Kinshasa, the Democratic Republic of Congo, from 30 September to 4 October 2019. This event was part of the annual review of progress at the level of economic communities (CER) of the Economic Community of Central African States (CEEAC).

On November 26-27, the national consultation workshop on the development of action plans for the

additional protocols of the Abidjan Convention was convened in Brazzaville.

As an epilogue, the environmental year ended with the negotiation phase at the 25th Conference of the Parties (COP) to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (COP25). On 2-14 December in Madrid, Spain, the government attended the 25th COP and was represented at the high-level round table of heads of state and government. In this capacity, the government highlighted initiatives to preserve and promote sustainable forest ecosystems management, peatlands, and mangroves. The government organized a meeting of the Congo Basin Climate Commission (CCBC) in order to present the first results of the Blue Fund for the Congo Basin foreshadowing study. It should be noted that negotiations also included Article 6 of the Paris Agreement, which was the core of the bilateral dialogue with some countries of Asia and Europe. Negotiations led either to consultations with the Francophonie Institute for Sustainable Development (IFDD) and other African countries on the occasion of Africa's Day.